

EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION OF PARTIAL DISCHARGE PATTERNS OF MINERAL OIL AND SYNTHETIC ESTER OIL

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Abstract:

As per IEC Standards, partial discharge (PD) are “localized electrical discharges that only partially bridge the insulation between conductors.” PD is local electrical stress on the insulation it can be internal or on the surface of the insulation. Petroleum-based mineral oil is traditionally used as insulation for power and distribution transformers over the century because of its scientifically proven advantages. But the use of mineral oil has disadvantages to the environment also PD effect significantly deteriorates insulation strength and can cause the transformer to fail. The ester-based Synthetic oil is been used as an alternative to mineral oil in recent decades due to its biodegradable and fire-resistant properties. In this paper, the partial discharge effect of mineral oil and synthetic ester oil is investigated experimentally as per IEC Standards and Phase Resolved Partial Discharge analyses are carried. The phase vs Charge, Charge vs Number of counts, and Phase vs Number of counts patterns are obtained individually for both oils, and results are compared and presented for PD deterioration effects.

Keywords: Partial discharge, Mineral oil, Synthetic ester, Phase-resolved partial discharge patterns, power transformer

Introduction

PD is a significant factor in the deterioration of high-voltage appliances. It slowly causes problems with continuous high-voltage stress causing progressive and irreversible damage to insulation systems. It creates a localized effect in temperature that produces a failure effect on insulation. The instant at which the insulation can no longer handle typical electrical stress results in complete dielectric breakdown and device failure, the process can continue in a positive feedback loop. PD testing and investigation need to be carried out in order to early detect the effect of PD. Different methods are used to identify PD, such as the detection through noise or sound, through light, and with radio frequency signals. The most preferable method is electrical detection as per IEC60270 Standard. [1]

Figure 1: causes of transformer failures

A Transformer is one of the key elements in the electrical power system. These transformers play an important role in the power grid to support the energy demand which is increasing day by day [2]. By 2040, it is projected that global demand for electricity may be around 80 percent higher than present consumption [3]. Transformers are generally more reliable equipment and are expected to serve for more than 40 years [4]. The transformer failure types or reasons are illustrated in the Figure. 1, as for the analysis Insulation breakdown is the main reason for the failure of transformers. Hence it is very essential to keep monitoring insulation health in a timely manner. Cellulose and oil are the commonly used insulations of power transformers due to their good reliability, low maintenance, and comparatively low price. Solid insulation cellulose is made from kraft paper or wood pulp. Provides outstanding oil impregnation characteristics with high geometric stability along with oil. Along with insulation, the cooling mechanism is obtained from liquid insulation. Petroleum-based mineral oil is predominately used for the impregnation process.

Functioning the transformer at higher temperatures is not favoured for cellulose material with mineral oil. The lifetime of the transformer will decrease radically when the transformer is run over the specified temperature.

Along with cooling, mineral oil provides a high breakdown strength, good arc extinguishing, and self-healing capacity. But they are very sensitive to environmental hazards when discarded directly to the soil. Recently, alternative liquids have been introduced such as natural and synthetic ester dielectric liquids which provide biodegradation and higher fire and flammable points. These liquids are shown to have higher breakdown voltage compared to mineral oil.

In open field areas such as wind power generating hills, PV panel mounted open places and in other locations where fire poses very danger to power equipment the synthetic ester can be used as an insulating liquid instead of mineral oil. From the experimental studies, it is stated there are carbon marks observed along the interface of the oil-pressboard due to the discharge phenomenon and changes in the Partial discharge for samples due to moisture [5]. But, investigation of phase-resolved partial discharge pattern in synthetic ester oil with pigtail specimen has been not reported [6].

The paper mainly focuses on the Investigation of the PD effect in paper-mineral oil and paper-Synthetic ester oil and compare their pattern to analyze the failure effect of transformers.

2. Experimental setup:

Figure 2: Pigtail sample

It involves the preparation of samples, finding the breakdown strength of oils, and PD experimentation. Analysis of Phase-resolved PD Patterns

2.1 Pigtail Sample preparation

The pigtail specimen consists of copper bar insulated with 3 layers of kraft paper arranged as shown in Figure.2 to represent the winding of the transformer. Mineral oil and synthetic ester oil [12][13] is procured from a renowned transformer oil vendor specified as per IEC standard. The same batch of oil is used for all the experiments.[7]

2.2 TEST CELL SETUP FOR PD:

Figure 3: Test cell Structure

The cell used to immerse pig-tail specimens into oil for PD experiments consists of a glass container sealed with rubber after filling the required quantity of oil. One end is connected to high voltage and another end to ground connection

2.3 PD Experimental Setup

230V/50Hz : Input Supply to HVCU

AT/HVCU : Auto Transformer/HV Control Unit

HVT : High Voltage Transformer

TC : Test Cell – Pigtail impregnated in oil

CT : Current Transformer

Ck : Coupling Capacitor

MI : Parallel RLC Matching Impedance Circuit

A1 : Amplifier Circuit for PD signal

A2 : Amplifier Circuit for Phase shifted Signal

Tanδ MS : Tanδ Measuring circuit

DSO : Digital Storage Oscilloscope

DAS : PC Based Data acquisition system

Figure 4: Synthetic ester oil Phase vs Charge pattern at start, Middle and end of experiment

The PD experimental setup [10] is shown in Figure 4 is designed as per IEC Standards which involve

PD free transformer, coupling capacitor, impedance matching circuit, PC-based data acquisition system, and digital storage oscilloscope. PD system need to be calibrated before actual experimentation [8]

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Phase-resolved partial discharge (PRPD) patterns obtained for pigtail specimen impregnated in mineral oil and pigtail specimen implanted in synthetic ester oil is discussed in this section.

3.1 Phase vs Charge Distribution

Figure. 5 shows Phase vs Charge PRPD pattern obtained for pigtail specimens impregnated in mineral oil and Figure. 6 shows Phase vs Charge PRPD pattern obtained for pigtail specimens impregnated in synthetic ester oil. The experiment is carried out for 04 hours duration and PD Phase vs charge data are captured throughout the experiment and PD patterns at the start, middle and end of the experiment are presented. The x-axis represents the Phase of occurrence and the y-axis represents the Charge magnitude in pC. It is clearly observed that PD charge magnitude is higher in mineral oil throughout the experiment. Also, the charge spread over the entire phase for mineral oil compared to synthetic ester oil. Dense heavy charges are observed for mineral oil over the positive and negative half cycle of input waveform varies as less dense charge magnitude is observed for synthetic ester oil. The charges start at the start of the phase whereas for synthetic ester oil phase of occurrence starts after 20°. From this pattern, it can clearly show that PD activities are more in mineral oil compared to synthetic ester oils.

3.2 Phase-Number of Counts (ϕ -N) distributions

Figure 7 and Figure 8 show Phase vs Number of counts distribution at the start, Middle, and end of the experiment for Mineral oil and synthetic ester oil respectively. The number of counts observed for mineral oil is higher and

Figure 1: Mineral oil Phase vs Charge PRPD Patterns at the start, middle and end of experiment

Figure 6: Synthetic ester oil Phase vs Charge pattern at start, Middle and end of experiment

Figure 7: Mineral oil Phase vs Number of Counts at the start, middle and end of experiment

Figure 8: Synthetic ester oil Phase vs Number of Counts at the start, middle and end of experiment

distributed over the entire phase while for synthetic ester oil number of counts is not distributed over the entire phase. Also, the number of counts is less in synthetic ester oil compared to mineral oil. From the phase number count, PD activities are lower in synthetic ester oil compared to mineral oil.

3.3 Charge-Number of Counts Distributions:

Figures 9 and 10 show Charge vs Number of counts distribution in pigtail specimen impregnated in mineral oil and synthetic ester oil respectively. From the figure 9 it is observed that number of counts are higher in mineral oil compared to synthetic ester oil.

The low magnitude charges observed in mineral oil are around 6000. The same low magnitude charges for synthetic ester oil observed at is around 1000. Less than 20pC charges are not observed in synthetic ester oil various few less than 20pC charges are observed in mineral oil.

Figure 9: Charge vs Number of Counts distribution in mineral oil at the start, middle and end of experiment

In the literature it is reported that [52] for pigtail specimen impregnated in mineral oil, the low pC charges are relatively higher in number compared to high pC charges. It is reported in the literature [9] that number of PD magnitude depends on the molecular structure of the ester oils and the number of PD pulses is lower in ester-based oils compared to mineral oil.

Figure 10: Charge vs Number of Counts distribution in synthetic ester oil at the start, middle and end of experiment

4. Conclusion:

In this work, the experiments were conducted by designing copper-paper insulation as pigtail specimen and PD data are extracted and PRPD analysis are carried out by impregnating specimens in mineral oil and synthetic ester oil. From the results it is observed that PD activities are more in mineral oil compared to synthetic ester oil. The synthetic ester oil can be used as alternative to mineral oil for transformer usage. More investigation need to be carried out with respect to other parameter such as moisture impact, surface discharge etc. for better understanding of synthetic ester compatibilities.

References:

- David Stewart, “what is partial discharge & how is it measured” pumps and system magazine march 2022
- Norasagepattanadech “partial discharge inception voltage characteristics of mineral oil” doctor of technical sciences thesis, graz university of technology, 2021
- Corporate headquarters, 2012 the outlook for energy: a view to 2040, 2012.
- Cigré working group 12.18, cigré brochure 227, guidelines for life management techniques for power transformers, january, 2003.
- H. Borsi, u. Schroder, “initiation and formation of partial discharges in mineral-based insulating oil,” iee trans. Dielectr. Electr. Insul., vol. 1, pp. 419-425, 1994.
- C. Thirumurugan, g. B. Kumbhar and r. Oruganti, "effects of impurities on surface discharges at synthetic ester/cellulose board," in iee transactions on dielectrics and electrical insulation, vol.

26, no. 1, pp. 64-71, feb. 2019, doi: 10.1109/tdei.2018.007439.

- Mahesh kumar k m, b.ramachandra, l.sanjeevkumar “analysis of phase resolved partial discharge patterns of kraft paper insulation impregnated in transformer mineral oil” ieee 2020 international conference on smart electronics and communication (icosec), trichy, india, 2020, pp. 1157-1161, doi: 10.1109/icosec49089.2020.9215344
- Mahesh kumar k m, b. Ramachandra “calibration of partial discharge measuring system by a reference square wave”, test engineering & management, january-february 2020 issn: 0193-4120 page no. 16276 – 1628
- M. Hikita et al., "partial discharge properties of ester oils having different molecular structures," 2012 ieee international symposium on electrical insulation, 2012, pp. 26-29, doi: 10.1109/elinsl.2012.6251419
- E. Commission, iec 60270, "high-voltage test techniques: partial discharge measurements," international electrotechnical commission, 2000.
- IEC 60296:2020, “fluids for electrotechnical applications – mineral insulating oils for electrical equipment” international standard.
- “transol synth 100”, transol synth 100 - savita chemicals. Synthetic transformer oil specification
- IEC 61099:2010, “insulating liquids – specifications for unused synthetic organic esters for electrical purposes”, 2nd edition, august 2010, <https://webstore.iec.ch/publication/4511>